

Cooperation in Microgrids through power exchange: an optimal sizing and operation approach

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Abstract

This paper proposes a novel model for the optimal design and power management of a microgrid. The key objective of the proposed model is to indicate the benefits of cooperation in terms of energy cost savings, carbon emission reduction and provision of energy self-sufficiency. The proposed cooperative configuration considers that buildings with different load patterns exchange power through a common DC bus, so that an optimum utilization of the energy generated by local renewables is achieved. The problem of selecting the optimal capacities of photovoltaic arrays, energy storage systems and inverters, as well as of determining the optimal daily power operation plan is formulated as a mixed integer linear programming problem, where the objective function is optimized based on the Nash bargaining method. The impact of the daily scheduling of the energy storage systems and electric vehicles, as well as the impact of power exchanges on the equipment

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sizing and vice-versa is also highlighted. We demonstrate the applicability and effectiveness of the proposed cooperative system on a representative Superblock of Barcelona; the results indicate that the proposed approach achieves significant operation cost (15.7%) and carbon emissions (12.9% in average) reduction compared to the case where no power exchange occurs.

Keywords: smart cities, microgrid, cooperative system, renewable energy sources, optimization.

Nomenclature			
$A_{PV}(b)$	building's b available surface for PVs	$P_L^{ESS}(b, t)$	power discharged from building's b ESS during time interval t
B	number of buildings	$P_L^{EV}(b, t)$	power discharged from building's b EVs during time interval t
$C(b)$	total cost for building b	$P_L^{MG}(b, t)$	power imported from the MG by the building b at time interval t
$C_I(b)$	installation cost for building b	$P_{MG}^{PV}(b, t)$	power generated by building's b PVs and sold to the MG at time interval t
$C_M(b)$	maintenance cost for building b	$P_{MG}^{ESS}(b, t)$	power stored in building's b ESS and sold to the MG at time interval t
$C_R(b)$	replacement cost for building b	$P^{PV,pro}(b, t)$	power generated by building's b PVs at time interval t
$C_O(b)$	electricity cost for building b from the main grid	$P^{PV,unit}(b, t)$	building's b PV normalized power generation
$C_c(b)$	carbon emission taxes cost for building b	$Q_{c,EV}(u, V_b)$	building's b EV u charging power
c_{BUS}	size of the DC bus	$Q_{c,EV}(u, V_b)$	building's b EV u discharging power
$Carb_{int}$	carbon intensity of the MG area	$Q_{EV}^{PV}(u, V_b)$	building's b EV u power provided by the PVs
$Carb_{tax}$	carbon emission taxes	$Q_{EV}^{ESS}(u, V_b)$	building's b EV u power provided by the ESS
d	discount rate	$Q_{EV}^{MG}(u, V_b)$	building's b EV u power provided by the MG
f	total savings	$Q_{EV}^G(u, V_b)$	building's b EV u power provided by the main grid
L_{BUS}	length of the DC bus	$R_{G,sell}(t)$	price of selling power to the main grid at time interval t
$n_{c,ESS}$	charging efficiency of the ESS	$R_{MG,sell}(t)$	price of selling power to the MG at time interval t
$n_{c,EV}$	charging efficiency of the EVs	$R_{G,buy}(t)$	price of buying power from the main grid at time interval t
$n_{d,ESS}$	discharging efficiency of the ESS	$R_{MG,buy}(t)$	price of buying power to the MG at time interval t
$n_{d,EV}$	discharging efficiency of the EVs	$R_{MG,buy}(t)$	price of buying power to the MG at time interval t
N_{ESS}	capacity of the ESS	$SoE_{ESS}(b, t)$	state of energy of building's b ESS at time interval t

n_{INV}	efficiency of the inverter	$SoE_{EV}(b, t)$	state of energy of building's b EVs at time interval t
$N_{INV(b)}$	capacity of building's b inverter	T	optimization horizon
n_{PV}	efficiency of the PV array	$u_{ESS}(b, t)$	binary variable used for the definition of the ESS operation
$N_{PV}(b)$	amount of 1 kW _p installed PV panels in building b	$u_{EV}(b, t)$	binary variable used for the definition of the EV operation
$P_{c,ESS}(b, t)$	charging power of building's b ESS during time interval t	$u_{ex}(b, t)$	binary variable used for the definition of the power exchanges in the MG
$P_{d,ESS}(b, t)$	discharging power of building's b ESS during time interval t	V_b	number of EVs in building b
$P_{c,EV}(b, t)$	charging power of building's b EVs during time interval t	Y	lifetime of the project
$P_{d,EV}(b, t)$	discharging power of building's b EVs during time interval t	Z_{ESS}	ESS's charging rate
$P_{ESS}^{PV}(b, t)$	power from building's b PV used for charging its ESS at time interval t	Z_{EV}	EV's charging rate
$P_{ESS}^{MG}(b, t)$	power from the MG used for charging building's ESS at time interval t	Greek symbols	
$P_{EV}^{PV}(b, t)$	power from building's b PVs used for charging the EVs at time interval t	λ_{PV}	amount of 1 kW _p PV panels that can be installed per m^2
$P_{EV}^{ESS}(b, t)$	power from building's b ESS used for charging EVs at time interval t	$\Phi(b)$	revenue for building b
$P_{EV}^{MG}(b, t)$	power from the MG used for charging building's b EVs at time interval t	μ_{BUS}	per unit annual maintenance cost
$P_{EV}^G(b, t)$	power from the main grid used for charging building's b EVs at time interval t	Subscripts	
$P_G^{PV}(b, t)$	power sold to the main grid by building b at time interval t	b	building index
$P_L(b, t)$	power demand of building b at time interval t	t	time interval index
$P_L^G(b, t)$	power imported from the grid by the building b at time interval t	u	EV index
$P_L^{PV}(b, t)$	power generated by building's b PVs at time interval t and used for self-consumption	y	year index

1. Introduction

The necessity for reducing pollution and increasing the quality of life in urban areas, as well as for developing a sustainable power system are the driving forces behind the advent of smart cities [1]. The concept of smart cities is highly promoted in Barcelona, Spain, where *Superblocks* are expected to be the basic cells for the organization of infrastructure and mobility networks, and for the organization of small-scale power networks. A Superblock is an urban area that is smaller than neighborhood but bigger than actual blocks, while its implementation targets not only a more sustainable mobility behavior of the citizens, but also an improvement of the buildings' self-sufficiency [2]. The latter ambitious target can be mainly achieved through the utilization of renewable energy sources (RES) and combined heat and power (CHP) units, so that the electrical and heat loads can be locally satisfied in an economic and environmental friendly way. The RES penetration can be further increased by integrating energy storage systems (ESS) and electric vehicles (EVs) that are equipped with vehicle-to-home (V2H) systems [3].

As the Superblock concept promotes the installation of distributed energy resources (DER), smart controllers and energy management units (EMUs) in urban buildings, the utilization of efficient energy management systems is vital for achieving significant energy savings and reducing carbon emissions. Consequently, the challenge is to develop models that coordinate the consumers so that they can achieve minimum dependency from the main distribution grid and maximum utilization of the energy generated from DER. These optimization models should take into account the buildings' load profiles and their seasonal variability, the electricity rates, the carbon emissions

and the corresponding taxes, as well as the power grid connection policies in order to determine the optimum capacities of the local DER and ESS, and the optimum power management of the selected units.

In this work, we examine the potential of building cooperation, by considering that Superblocks are small-scale power networks, i.e. microgrids (MGs), consisting of different building types, and we propose a mixed integer linear model (MILP) model for determining the optimal sizes of the equipment to be installed in each building such as, PVs, ESS and inverters. The various buildings are interconnected through a DC bus, which enables the power exchanges among them. The daily power operation plan is also determined, which refers to the amount of PV power that is used for self-consumption, for being stored to the ESS and for being sold to the main grid. It also refers to the optimum ESS and EVs' charge and discharge scheduling, as well as to the optimum power exchanges taking place among the participants. Three different design scenarios are compared with the baseline scenario, which considers that all buildings are supplied with power by the main grid and the only available smart asset is the V2H system. The first design scenario considers that the buildings are equipped with PVs, ESS, inverters and V2H systems, but they do not exchange power. In the second scenario, we apply the proposed cooperative approach that enables the various buildings to exchange power through a common DC bus. Moreover, the third scenario extends the second scenario and indicates how the achieved benefits are fairly allocated among the participants.

The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows: a) the proposed model shows not only the benefits of multiple building cooperation

on the operation of the system, but it also indicates how the system's sizing affects the operation plan and vice-versa. b) The proposed work goes beyond the state of the art for the association between sizing and operation of MGs by presenting a realistic case study where buildings with different load profiles (i.e. residential, commercial, and administrative buildings), located within a MG, form a coalition. c) The optimal sizing and operation plan of building coalitions is determined based on the Nash bargain method, through which the benefits of cooperation are fairly distributed among the participants. The main aim of building coalitions is the reduction of each participant's costs compared to the case where no co-operation takes place. A common approach that is used for optimizing building coalitions is to minimize the total cost of all participants. However, this method may lead to an unequal distribution of the coalition benefits. The Nash bargain method optimizes the entire MG performance whilst guaranteeing that the profits of co-operation are fairly distributed among the participants. An additional advantage of the present approach is the consideration of the DC bus. This configuration facilitates the cooperation of buildings that are fed by different distribution transformers. The majority of the studies in the literature consider that all buildings (or loads) are located at the low voltage of the same distribution transformer, and hence they can exchange power through the PCC. However, for buildings that are willing to cooperate, and they are neither connected to the same transformer nor to a common DC bus, the only way for exchanging power is through the medium voltage distribution line. In that case, the decisions for the optimal power flows are taken by the distribution system operator (DSO). The configuration proposed in this work removes

the aforementioned restriction, while it guarantees the self-management of the MG, and ensures that power exchanges take place only among the MG participants. The evaluation of the performance of the proposed cooperative approach is realized by considering a representative Superblock in the city of Barcelona that comprises of buildings with diverse power consumption patterns. The results of the proposed approach indicate a significant reduction of the operational cost by 34.6% compared to the baseline scenario (where buildings obtain energy by the main grid only) and by 15.7% compared to a MG case where no power exchange occurs, as well as a reduction of the carbon emissions by 65.3% compared to the baseline scenario and by 12.9% compared to the non-cooperative MG.

This work is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the related work, while Section 3 presents the MILP model for determining the optimum sizes of the buildings' equipment, and the daily power operation plan. Section 4 presents the examined case study and the corresponding results. Finally, Section 5 concludes this work.

2. Related work

Optimization models have been widely used for the derivation of the optimal solution in microgrids; the interested reader may refer to [16] for a review of the most significant optimal power flow approaches in smart grids and MGs, and to [17] for optimization approaches that target to maximize the effect of demand response mechanisms in the operation of smart grids. However, there exists a significant number of research approaches that deal with the optimum operation scheduling and/or the optimal sizing of a MG.

In this section we initially review the former optimization approaches, while we also provide a discussion on the state-of-the art methods that deal with both the optimal operation and sizing of MGs.

The problem of determining the optimum power operation plan of the various DER and ESS installed in MGs has been greatly studied in the literature, through the definition of energy management systems (EMS) that target to optimally utilize the energy produced by DER and/or stored to ESS. Marzband et al. has provided an extensive work on energy management systems for MG applications, where various optimization models has been proposed for solving the optimal operation point within a MG, while experimental setups are used in order to validate the proposed approaches ([18]-[24]). Zhang et al. [4] propose an energy management scheme for a grid-connected MG, which contains conventional DER, RES and ESS. The objective of this scheme is to minimize the MG net cost, which includes the operating costs of conventional DER and ESS, the cost of transactions between the main grid and the MG and the utility of dispatchable loads. Hosseinzadeh et al. [5], apply the MILP technique for minimizing the operational cost of an isolated DC/AC MG, by maximizing the utilization of RES and minimizing the usage of fuel-based generators. The proposed approach considers the application of a DC bus, however, a single type of load is taken into account. Paterakis et al. [6] deal with the optimal operation of a neighborhood, which consists of multiple smart homes. The MG is fed by a distribution transformer, while each home contains RES, ESS, controllable appliances and EVs. Furthermore, each home exchanges energy with other homes, and with the main grid through the point of common

coupling (PCC). The operation plan of the considered MG is obtained by using the MILP technique with the objective of minimizing the total energy cost. On the other hand, in [7], the optimal daily generation and load management plan of a smart distribution network is determined by utilizing a multi-objective glow-worm swarm optimization (GSO) algorithm. A model predictive control (MPC) for the optimal charge and discharge scheduling of ESS, as well as the optimal power exchanges among interconnected MGs is presented in [8]. The MPC technique is appropriate for optimizing the short-term operation of MGs, since it mitigates the impacts of forecast errors on the optimality of the solution.

There are also several studies that deal not only with the optimal operation, but also the optimal MG sizing. Mehleri et al. [9] propose a model for the optimal design of a heating network that allows heat exchanges among the various buildings. However, electricity exchanges are not taken into account in [9]. On the other hand, Di Zhang et al. [10] consider a MG where electricity can be transferred among different buildings. The Nash bargaining method is used which fairly maximizes the benefits of all participants by determining the intra-MG electricity transfer price, the electricity flow between sites, the size of the selected power units and their operation plan. An interesting approach regarding the sizing and operation of MGs is introduced in [11], where the load pattern of a smart home is induced by the implementation of a demand response scheme, which in turn affects the sizing of PVs and ESS. Similar is the concept in [12] where it is examined how the load flexibility affects the sizing of PVs, ESS and inverters of a residential MG. In the aforementioned studies ([9]-[12]) the optimal MG design and power

management problem is formulated as a MILP problem. In contrast, the GSO optimization method is utilized in [13], while a swarm based artificial bee colony algorithm is applied in [14] for deriving the optimal equipment capacities of a DC/AC MG. A DC/AC MG is also considered in [15] where the system's design is determined through a multi-objective genetic algorithm.

In this paper, we go beyond the state of the art by proposing a cooperative approach in order to achieve minimum dependency from the main distribution grid and maximize the utilization of the energy generated from DER. The proposed method provides not only the optimal operation of the buildings, as in the case of [4]-[8], [18]-[24], but it also provides that optimal size of the system that guarantees minimum operation cost. The association between sizing and MG operation is also studied in [11]-[15]; however, these studies consider only one type of load. The latter assumption may lead to non-optimal results when applied to realistic cases where the MG comprises of buildings with diverse load profiles. The proposed approach considers the realistic case where buildings that may have different power consumption patterns form a coalition and exchange energy in order to minimize the dependency from the main grid. Moreover, the proposed optimization model considers the Nash bargain method in order to provide a fair distribution of the cooperation benefits to all MG participants. The same method is also applied in [10], however, the operation of PVs, ESS and EVs is neglected in that model, as well as the utilization of the DC bus. The DC bus feature is an additional advantage of the proposed approach, which is introduced in order to overcome the limitation of a single distribution transformer, as it is considered in the studies in [6]-[8] and [10]; therefore, the proposed ap-

proach can be applied to in cases where buildings are connected to different distribution transformers.

3. Mathematical Model

We consider a MG that consists of B buildings. The various buildings are interconnected through a DC bus, while they are also equipped with an EMU and local controllers for each dispatchable source, such as the ESS and the V2H system. A communication network connects the EMU of each building with the MG central controller (MGCC), which provides the power scheduling plan [25], [26]. In the following subsections we initially determine the equations for the different parts of the MG, and then we proceed with the definition of the proposed optimization model, which aims at obtaining the optimum size of PVs, DC/AC inverters and ESS for each building, as well as the optimum power management of the MG.

3.1. Power Balance

The power demand $P_L(b, t)$ of each building b ($b = 1, \dots, B$) at any time interval t is satisfied by importing power from the main grid $P_L^G(b, t)$, by the power produced by the PVs $P_L^{PV}(b, t)$, and it is used for self-consumption, by the power $P_L^{ESS}(b, t)$ which is discharged from the ESS, and by the power $P_L^{MG}(b, t)$ that is imported through the DC bus:

$$P_L(b, t) = P_L^G(b, t) + P_L^{PV}(b, t) + P_L^{ESS}(b, t) + P_L^{MG}(b, t) \quad (1)$$

3.2. PV Operation

At any time interval t , the total amount of power $P^{PV,pro}(b, t)$ produced by the PV array of building b is determined by multiplying the amount $N_{PV}(b)$ of 1 kW_p installed PV panels with the normalized production $P^{PV,unit}(t)$ ([27]):

$$P^{PV,pro}(b, t) = N_{PV}(b)P^{PV,unit}(t) \quad (2)$$

The size of the PV array is limited by the available surface $A_{PV}(b)$ of each building and the amount λ_{PV} of 1 kW_p panels that can be installed per available m²:

$$N_{PV}(b) \leq A_{PV}(b)\lambda_{PV} \quad (3)$$

Part of the power $P^{PV,pro}(b, t)$ is transferred through the DC/AC inverter to the AC side for covering the building's load ($P_L^{PV}(b, t)$) and for charging the EVs' ($P_{EV}^{PV}(b, t)$). Part of the produced power is also used for charging the ESS ($P_{ESS}^{PV}(b, t)$), while other parts are sold to the main grid ($(P_G^{PV}(b, t))$) and to the other MG participants ($(P_{MG}^{PV}(b, t))$) through the DC bus:

$$P^{PV,pro}(b, t)n_{PV} = \frac{P_L^{PV}(b, t) + P_{EV}^{PV}(b, t) + P_G^{PV}(b, t)}{n_{INV}} + P_{ESS}^{PV}(b, t) + P_{MG}^{PV}(b, t) \quad (4)$$

where n_{PV} and n_{INV} denote the efficiency of the PV array and the inverter, respectively.

3.3. ESS Operation

The ESS' operation is characterized by the charging power $P_{c,ESS}(b, t)$, which is provided by the PVs ($P_{ESS}^{PV}(b, t)$) and by the power $P_{ESS}^{MG}(b, t)$, which is imported from the MG ((5)). According to (6), the ESS' discharging power

$P_{d,ESS}(b, t)$ is used for satisfying the local load ($P_L^{ESS}(b, t)$), for covering part of the EVs' needs ($P_{EV}^{ESS}(b, t)$), and for being sold to other MG users ($P_{MG}^{ESS}(b, t)$). The parameters $n_{c,ESS}$ and $n_{d,ESS}$ define the ESS' charging and discharging efficiency, respectively. Furthermore, constraints (7) and (8) assure that the ESS is not charged and discharged at the same time. This is achieved by using the parameter Ξ , which is a very large number, and the binary variable $u_{ESS}(b, t)$. Constraints (9) and (10) define the upper limit of the charging/discharging power of the ESS, which is a function of the ESS' charging rate Z_{ESS} and the capacity N_{ESS} . The state of energy $SoE_{ESS}(b, t)$ of the ESS at any time interval t is described by (11); it is equal to the state of energy (SoE) of the previous interval $SoE_{ESS}(b, t - 1)$ plus the energy that is transferred to the ESS (if it is charged during t), or minus the discharged energy (if it is discharged during t). Δt is the duration of the optimization intervals, while $SoE_{ESS}(b, t_0)$ is the SoE at the beginning of the optimization horizon. Since $SoE_{ESS}(b, t_0)$ is used only for the determination of $SoE_{ESS}(b, 1)$, the binary parameter $u_{ESS}^{init}(b, t)$ is required, which is equal to 1 for the first time interval and equal to 0 for $t > 1$. Constraint (12) sets the minimum and the maximum SoE of the ESS, while constraint (13) imposes that the SoE at the beginning of the optimization horizon equals the SoE at the end of the optimization horizon.

$$P_{c,ESS}(b, t) = [P_{ESS}^{PV}(b, t) + P_{ESS}^{MG}(b, t)]n_{c,ESS} \quad (5)$$

$$P_{d,ESS}(b, t)n_{d,ESS} = \frac{P_L^{ESS}(b, t) + P_{EV}^{ESS}(b, t)}{n_{INV}} + P_{MG}^{ESS}(b, t) \quad (6)$$

$$P_{c,ESS}(b, t) \leq \Xi u_{ESS}(b, t) \quad (7)$$

$$P_{d,ESS}(b, t) \leq \Xi[1 - u_{ESS}(b, t)] \quad (8)$$

$$P_{c,ESS}(b, t) \leq Z_{ESS}N_{ESS}(b) \quad (9)$$

$$P_{d,ESS}(b, t) \leq Z_{ESS}N_{ESS}(b) \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} SoE_{ESS}(b, t) = & SoE_{ESS}(b, t - 1) + P_{c,ESS}(b, t)\Delta t - \\ & P_{d,ESS}(b, t)\Delta t + u_{ESS}^{init}(b, t)SoE_{ESS}(b, t_0) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$SoE_{ESS, \min} \leq SoE_{ESS}(b, t) \leq SoE_{ESS, \max} \quad (12)$$

$$SoE_{ESS}(b, T) = SoE_{ESS}(b, t_0) \quad (13)$$

3.4. EVs Operation

We consider that building b , ($b = 1, \dots, B$) contains a set of V_b EVs equipped with the V2H technology. Relations (14)-(20) describe the operation of each single EV, while (21)-(26) describe the way building b schedules the charging and discharging procedures of the EV set V_b . As (14) denotes, the EVs' charging power $Q_{c,EV}(v, t)$ ($v=(1, \dots, V_b)$) is provided by the PVs $Q_{EV}^{PV}(v, t)$, by the ESS $Q_{EV}^{ESS}(v, t)$, by the power imports from the MG $Q_{EV}^{MG}(v, t)$, as well as by the power imports from the main grid $Q_{EV}^G(v, t)$. According to (15), the EVs' discharging power $Q_{d,EV}(b, t)$ is only used for satisfying the local load $P_L^{EV}(b, t)$. The parameters $n_{c,EV}$ and $n_{d,EV}$ define the charging and discharging efficiency of the EVs. Constraints (16) and (17) assure that the EVs are not charged and discharged at the same time, while they also define the upper limit of the charging/discharging power. Additionally, in the aforementioned relations, Z_{EV} denotes the EVs' charging/discharging rate, while $u_{EV}(v, t)$ is a binary variable. The EVs' state of energy $SoE_{EV}(v, t)$ at any time interval t is described by (18). Similar to

the ESS case, $SoE_{EV}(v, t)$ is equal to the SoE of the previous time interval $SoE_{EV}(v, t - 1)$ plus the energy that is transferred to the EV or minus the discharged energy. Constraint (19) defines the minimum and the maximum SoE values, while (20) defines the EVs' arrival and departure SoE.

$$Q_{c,EV}(v, t) = [Q_{EV}^{PV}(v, t) + Q_{EV}^{ESS}(v, t) + Q_{EV}^{MG}(v, t) + Q_{EV}^G(v, t)]n_{c,EV} \quad (14)$$

$$Q_{d,EV}(v, t)n_{d,EV} = Q_L^{EV}(v, t) \quad (15)$$

$$Q_{c,EV}(v, t) \leq Z_{EV}(v)u_{EV}(v, t) \quad (16)$$

$$Q_{d,EV}(v, t) \leq Z_{EV}(v)[1 - u_{EV}(v, t)] \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} SoE_{EV}(v, t) = & SoE_{EV}(v, t - 1) + Q_{c,EV}(v, t)\Delta t - \\ & Q_{d,EV}(v, t)\Delta t + u_{EV}^{init}(v, t)SoE_a(v, T_a(v)) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

$$SoE_{EV,\min} \leq SoE_{EV}(v, t) \leq SoE_{EV,\max} \quad (19)$$

$$SoE_{EV}(v, T_a(v)) = SoE_a(v), SoE_{EV}(v, T_d(v)) = SoE_d(v) \quad (20)$$

The relations (14)-(20) hold for $T_a(v) \leq t \leq T_d(v)$, where $T_a(v)$ and $T_d(v)$ define the EVs' arrival and departure times. Furthermore, $u_{EV}^{init}(v, t) = 1$ for $t = T_a(v)$, while $u_{EV}^{init}(v, t) = 0$ in any other case. The total amount of the EVs' charging power is provided by the PVs, the ESS, the MG and the main grid. These quantities are calculated by (21)-(25), respectively:

$$P_{c,EV}(b, t) = P_{EV}^{PV}(b, t) + P_{EV}^{ESS}(b, t) + P_{EV}^{MG}(b, t) + P_{EV}^G(b, t) \quad (21)$$

$$P_{EV}^{PV}(b, t) = \sum_{v \in V_b} Q_{EV}^{PV}(v, t) \quad (22)$$

$$P_{EV}^{ESS}(b, t) = \sum_{v \in V_b} Q_{EV}^{ESS}(v, t) \quad (23)$$

$$P_{EV}^{MG}(b, t) = \sum_{v \in V_b} Q_{EV}^{MG}(v, t) \quad (24)$$

$$P_{EV}^G(b, t) = \sum_{v \in V_b} Q_{EV}^G(v, t) \quad (25)$$

In addition, as (26) denotes, the total amount of the EVs' discharging power is used for satisfying the local load.

$$P_{d,EV}(b, t) = P_L^{EV}(b, t) = \sum_{v \in V_b} Q_L^{EV}(v, t) \quad (26)$$

3.5. Inverter Operation

The power that is transferred from the DC side of each building to the AC side through the DC/AC inverter should be lower than the inverter's nominal capacity $N_{INV}(b)$; therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} P_L^{PV}(b, t) + P_{EV}^{PV}(b, t) + P_G^{PV}(b, t) + P_L^{ESS}(b, t) + \\ P_{EV}^{ESS}(b, t) + P_L^{MG}(b, t) + P_{EV}^{MG}(b, t) \leq n_{INV} N_{INV}(b) \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

3.6. Microgrid Power Exchanges

At any time interval t , the amount of power that is bought by the buildings b (left hand side of (28)) equals the amount of power that is sold by the buildings b' (right hand side of (28)):

$$\sum_b \frac{P_L^{MG}(b, t) + P_{EV}^{MG}(b, t)}{n_{INV}} + P_{ESS}^{MG}(b, t) = \sum_{b'} P_{MG}^{PV}(b', t) + P_{MG}^{ESS}(b', t) \quad (28)$$

As expressed by (29) and (30), the buildings cannot sell and buy power at the same time:

$$P_L^{MG}(b, t) + P_{ESS}^{MG}(b, t) + P_L^G \leq \Xi u_{ex}(b, t) \quad (29)$$

$$P_{MG}^{PV}(b, t) + P_{MG}^{ESS}(b, t) + P_G^{PV}(b, t) \leq \Xi[1 - u_{ex}(b, t)] \quad (30)$$

where $u_{ex}(b, t)$ is a binary variable.

3.7. Economic Analysis

The present value of the cost $C(b)$ of each building participating in the MG is described by the following equation:

$$C(b) = C_I(b) + C_M(b) + C_R(b) + C_O(b) + C_C(b) - \Phi(b) \quad (31)$$

Based on the aforementioned relation, the present value of the building's b cost $C(b)$ is equal to the the installation cost $C_I(b)$, the maintenance cost $C_M(b)$, the replacement cost $C_R(b)$ of the equipment, the cost $C_O(b)$ of buying electricity from the main grid and from the other MG participants, the cost $C_c(b)$ due to the carbon emission taxes, as well as the revenue $\Phi(b)$ of each building due to the power that exports to the MG and to the main grid. The installation cost $C_I(b)$ is given by multiplying the size by the per unit cost of each technology:

$$C_I(b) = c_{PV}N_{PV}(b) + c_{ESS}N_{ESS}(b) + c_{INV}N_{INV}(b) + \frac{c_{BUS}L_{BUS}}{B} \quad (32)$$

The maintenance cost $C_M(b)$ is derived by multiplying the size of each asset by their per unit annual maintenance cost:

$$C_M(b) = \sum_{y=1}^Y \frac{\mu_{PV}N_{PV}(b) + \mu_{ESS}N_{ESS}(b) + \mu_{INV}N_{INV}(b) + (\mu_{BUS}L_{BUS})/B}{(1+d)^y} \quad (33)$$

The replacement cost $C_R(b)$ is obtained by the following relation:

$$C_R(b) = \sum_{i=1}^{rep(tec)} \frac{c_{PV}N_{PV}(b) + c_{ESS}N_{ESS}(b) + c_{INV}N_{INV}(b) + (c_{BUS}L_{BUS})/B}{(1+d)^{iY_{rep}(tec)}} \quad (34)$$

where $rep(tec)$ denotes the number of replacements required for each candidate technology (PV, ESS, inverter, DC bus), while $Y_{rep}(tec)$ indicates the year of the first replacement. The electricity supplying cost $C_O(b)$ is derived by the following relation (35), where $R_{G,buy}(t)$ and $R_{MG,buy}$ denote the price of buying electricity from the main grid and the MG, respectively:

$$C_O(b) = \sum_{y=1}^Y \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T [P_L^G(b,t) + P_{EV}^G(b,t)]R_{G,buy}(t)\Delta t + [\frac{P_{MG}^{MG}(b,t) + P_{EV}^{MG}(b,t)}{n_{INV}} + P_{ESS}^{MG}(b,t)]R_{MG,buy}\Delta t}{(1+d)^y} \quad (35)$$

The cost $C_c(b)$ due to carbon emissions depends on the amount of power imported from the main grid, the carbon intensity $Carb_{int}$ of the area where the MG is installed, as well as by the carbon taxes $Carb_{tax}$:

$$C_c(b) = \sum_{y=1}^Y \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T [P_L^G(b,t) + P_{EV}^G(b,t)]Carb_{int}Carb_{tax}\Delta t}{(1+d)^y} \quad (36)$$

Finally, the revenue $\Phi(b)$ of each building due to the energy exports to the MG and to the main grid is calculated as follows, where $R_{G,sell}(t)$ and $R_{MG,sell}$

are the prices of selling power to the main grid and the MG, respectively:

$$\Phi(b) = \sum_{y=1}^Y \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T P_G^{PV}(b, t) R_{G, sell}(t) \Delta t + [P_{MG}^{PV}(b, t) + P_{MG}^{ESS}(b, t)] R_{MG, sell} \Delta t}{(1 + d)^y} \quad (37)$$

For the prices of buying and selling energy to the grid and to the MG, the following holds: $R_{G, buy}(t) > R_{MG, buy} = R_{MG, sell} > R_{G, sell}(t)$, where $R_{G, buy}$ and $R_{MG, buy}$ are the prices for buying power from the main grid and the MG, respectively. This pricing scheme promotes the cooperation among the MG users for two reasons; the power imported through the DC bus is cheaper than the power imported from the main grid, while it is more profitable for the participants to export their excess power to the DC bus than to the main grid. Finally, it should be noted that for the calculation of the present values of the costs in (33), (35) and (36), and of the revenue in (37), the discount rate d is used since the optimization horizon T is one year, while Y denotes the lifetime of the project.

3.8. Objective Function

The optimal equipment capacities and power management of the MG are obtained based on the Nash bargain method. The objective function consists of the product of savings of each building. The savings refer to the difference between the total cost $C'(b)$ of the system when power exchanges among the various buildings are not taking place minus the total cost $C(b)$ when the buildings are interconnected via the DC bus:

$$f = \prod_{b=1}^B SAV(b) = \prod_{b=1}^B [C'(b) - C(b)] \quad (38)$$

It should be noted that by implementing the Nash Bargain method, each cost $C(b)$ yields minimum value whilst trying to achieve the maximum objective value in (38). As a result, both respective benefits and overall performance are guaranteed. Furthermore, the cost $C'(b)$ is obtained by minimizing (31) subject to (1)-(30), where the variables correlated with the MG operation (variables that have either a MG superscript or a MG subscript) are not taken into account in the $C'(b)$ calculation. The objective function in (38) is non-linear, and therefore, it is linearized via logarithmic differentiation as $\ln f = \sum_{b=1}^B \ln[C'(b) - C(b)]$, which can be written as follows [10]:

$$z = \sum_{b=1}^B \sum_{w=1}^W C(b, w) \lambda(b, w) \quad (39)$$

$$\sum_{w=1}^W C(b, w) \lambda(b, w) = C(b) \quad (40)$$

$$\sum_{w=1}^W \lambda(b, w) = 1 \quad (41)$$

$$\lambda(b, w) \geq 0 \quad (42)$$

The values of the parameter $C(b, w)$ range between the upper bound, which is equal to $C'(b)$, and the minimum bound $C''(b)$, which is obtained by minimizing (31) subject to (1)-(30). Therefore, the optimal capacities of the candidate technologies, and the optimal daily power operation plan are obtained by maximizing (39) subject to (1)-(30) and (40)-(42).

4. Case Study

4.1. Input Data

For the evaluation of the proposed approach we consider the load profiles of six neighboring buildings located in the Poblenou superblock, Barcelona, Spain. Specifically, the hourly power consumption per m^2 for two schools, an office building, a public building, which operates as a civic center, and two residential buildings are considered. The hourly power consumption values are provided by the municipality of Barcelona. The total surface of each building and the available surface for installing PV panels are reported in Table 1. It is to be noted that, for each building, 1 kW_p is installed for every 7 m^2 available surface. The hourly PV production of a 1kW_p PV array located in Barcelona is obtained by [27]. The values of the PV array efficiency, the ESS' specifications [28], the inverters' efficiency [14] and the total length of the DC bus are presented in Table 2.

We also consider that the two residential buildings are equipped with V2H systems. The specifications (Table 3) of Nissan Leaf are taken into account for the EVs [29], since it is the most popular EV model in Spain [30]. The first residential building contains 18 EVs, while the second contains 12 EVs. For presentation purposes, it is assumed that all EVs have the same arrival and departure times, and follow the same charging and discharging scheduling. The EVs' arrival SoE is calculated based on their average covered distance between two consecutive charging events and their power consumption [31]. By assuming that all EVs depart from the residential buildings after a full battery recharge and arrive after consuming 9 kWh [31], $SoE_a(v)$ is equal to 15 kWh.

Tables 4 and 5 report the economic data that are taken into account for the optimization process. The considered electricity rates $R_{G,buy}(t)$ differ between winter and summer months [32]. In both cases, the lower rate is between 00:00-08:00. In winter months, the higher rate is between 18:00-22:00, while the peak price period for the summer months is between 11:00-15:00. For the remaining hours the medium rate is activated. The rates of energy transactions $R_{MG,buy}(t)$ and $R_{MG,sell}(t)$ among the MG users is assumed to be 40% lower than the corresponding rates $R_{G,buy}(t)$, while the price $R_{G,sell}(t)$ of selling energy back to the grid is 90% lower than the corresponding buying prices. Table 4 also presents the carbon intensity $Carb_{int}$ in Spain [33], while it is also considered that $Carb_{tax}=0.03$ €/Kg [34]. Moreover, the project lifetime Y is 20 years [14], and the discount rate d is assumed to be 3%. It should be noted that the time interval t is considered to be equal to 1 hour; by applying this value to the proposed optimization model, the maximum computational time for the derivation of the results is equal to 528 sec. by using a core i5 2.4 GHz CPU and 8 GB RAM, which is satisfactory both for the design and the daily operational plan for the MG.

4.2. Design Results

Three different scenarios are evaluated regarding the optimal MG design. For each scenario, the results regarding the size of the PVs, the inverters and the ESS for each building are reported in Table 6. The resulted savings of each design scenario are compared with the present value of the operation cost of the main grid scenario. This baseline scenario considers that all buildings are provided with energy by the main grid only, while it is also assumed that the V2H system is the only available smart asset. The CO₂ reduction of the

3 scenarios compared to the CO₂ emissions under the baseline scenario is also reported.

The first scenario considers that no power exchanges take place among the various buildings. Any power surplus is sold back to the main grid at a price $R_{G,sell}(t)$. The sizing results are obtained by minimizing (31) subject to (1)-(30), where the variables associated with the MG operation are not taken into account. Under the first scenario, each building achieves remarkable savings (by 29.8%) compared to the baseline scenario, while the CO₂ emissions are also noticeably reduced (by 52.5%), due to the combined operation of the PVs and ESS. The second scenario considers the proposed cooperative scenario, where 6 buildings form a MG and exchange power through a common DC bus. The sizing results for this scenario are obtained by minimizing the summation $\sum_B C(b)$ subject to (1)-(30). This configuration increases the savings compared to the first scenario (by 15.7%), despite the fact that the total size of the PVs, the inverters and the ESS is greater compared to the first scenario. The CO₂ emissions are also reduced (by 12.9%), since less amount of energy is imported from the main grid. The second scenario indicates the benefits of cooperation in terms of emissions and costs reduction; however, the achieved savings are not equally distributed among the participants. For example, the additional savings of the second scenario compared to the first scenario for School 1 are 6,48 k€, while the additional savings for the Residential 1 are 51,51 k€. This unfairness is avoided in the third scenario by implementing the Nash bargain method (maximize (39) subject to (1)-(30) and (40)-(42)). As Table 6 reports, the total savings achieved due to the cooperation of the six buildings are the same as in the second

scenario, but they are equally distributed among the participating buildings. Therefore, the proposed approach can provide the optimal MG design parameters, especially when the MG comprises of buildings with diverse power consumption patterns and a fair distribution of the savings is desired.

4.3. Daily Power Operation Plan for Scenario 3

As already stated, the different load profiles of the various buildings create a high power exchange potential, which in turn increases the system's savings and decreases the CO₂ emissions. Fig. 1 shows the hourly power exchanges that take place among the MG participants during a winter and a summer month. The optimal daily power operation plan is obtained by maximizing (39) subject to (1)-(30) and (40)-(42). The results of Fig. 1 show that the power exchanges are highly affected by the day type and the season. The residential buildings mainly buy power on Sundays, while they provide their excess power on Mondays when their demands are low and the PV production is high. The schools buy power in winter weekdays during their peak load, while they sell power in any other case. The public building sells power during the winter months, while it buys a significant amount of power during its peak load; the later exchanges take place on weekday evenings of summer months. Lastly, the office building sells power in weekends and buys power on weekdays; these power exchanges both take place during winter and summer months.

Fig. 2 indicates how each entity of the system covers the hourly load profile of one of the schools, the office and the public buildings, as well as of one of the residential buildings. The corresponding charts refer to a Sunday and a Monday of February. The school and the office have similar

load patterns. On Sundays, the load is low during the whole day. In both cases, during the low rate period (00:00-08:00), the demand is satisfied by importing power from the main grid. The medium rate period (08:00-18:00) coincides with the PV production hours; hence, the two buildings either sell power to the MG or to the main grid or charge their ESS, while during the peak price period (18:00-22:00) they discharge the energy stored in the ESS. The public building shows a similar behavior as the school and the office buildings on Sundays, while the residential building takes advantage of the power surplus in the other buildings by importing power, which is used for charging the EVs and for covering the load during the peak price period. On the other hand, during Mondays the school and the office import power from the MG for satisfying their peak load, which coincides with the medium rate period. The peak demands of the public and residential buildings coincide with the peak price period: the public building covers a great amount of its power needs by importing power from the MG and by discharging its ESS, while the load of the residential buildings is satisfied by the ESS and EVs' discharging.

Fig. 3 presents the power dispatch of the four buildings in July when both the load and the PV production are higher and the peak price period is between 11:00-15:00. The school and the office behave in a similar way as in February. The main differences are observed in the public and residential buildings. The school imports a large amount of power from the MG, on Mondays, during the peak price and the peak load periods. Besides, the residential buildings import a great amount of power on Sundays and during the evening hours for charging the EVs and for satisfying their load. This

amount of power is mainly provided by the ESS of the school and the office buildings, which have low energy demands on Sundays.

Fig. 4 compares the EVs' charge and discharge scheduling in July. The charts on the left and the right part of Fig. 5 refer to the baseline and the third scenario, respectively. Under the baseline scenario, the EVs are charged during the low price period, while the stored energy is discharged during the evening, which is the peak load period of the residential building. The schedule is similar for both weekends and weekdays. Under the third scenario the schedule is completely different, especially on weekends. The EVs satisfy part of the load at night, while they are charged during the PV production hours. A great amount of the charging power is provided by the excess power of the other MG participants. The advantage of this configuration is twofold; buildings with energy surplus eject their excess power to the DC bus instead of ejecting it to the main grid. Hence, they achieve higher revenues because the price of selling energy to the MG is higher than the price of selling energy to the main grid. The residential buildings are also benefited because they use the energy stored to the EVs for satisfying their peak demand.

5. Conclusion

This article highlights the advantages of cooperation among urban buildings that formulate a microgrid and are able to exchange energy in order to achieve increased self-sufficiency and reduced carbon emissions. The proposed cooperative model targets the determination of the optimal capacities of the buildings' equipment(PVs, inverters and ESS), as well as their optimal power management, by incorporating the buildings' power consumption

patterns, the electricity prices and the carbon emission taxes. We consider that the buildings are interconnected through a DC bus which facilitates the self-management of the MG and assures that power exchanges take place among the participants. The proposed configuration indicates that power exchanges affect the equipment sizing and vice-versa. Furthermore, the MG participants' energy supply and carbon emission costs are lower than the corresponding costs when no power exchanges take place, while, by applying the Nash bargain method, the savings achieved are equally distributed among the participants. The proposed cooperative scheme is therefore a viable solution not only for the optimal determination of the buildings' equipment size, but, mainly for the significant reduction of the urban buildings' dependence on the main grid, as well as of their carbon footprint.

The proposed cooperative scheme considers that each building is equipped with PVs, ESS and EVs, which increase the electrical energy self-sufficiency of the MG. However, units that satisfy the buildings' thermal and cooling loads are not taken into account. For example, CHP units that provide both electrical and thermal energy may increase the self-sufficiency of the MG. Such units will be taken into account in our future work, where the optimal design and operation of an islanded MG will be examined, where demand response schemes will be also incorporated as an effective solution to reduce the microgrid's power consumption especially in peak demand periods.

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